

Rac-5f

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-105-RAC-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	43	Acq. Method Set:	30%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 3 105 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/18/2022 9:28:03 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/19/2022 10:38:33 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.311	1987468	49.32	103496
2	15.820	2042588	50.68	64825

Asy-5f

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-3-105-ASY-30%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	
Vial:	78	Acq. Method Set:	30%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	XT 3 105 ASY
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	60.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	4/18/2022 10:48:23 PM CST		
Date Processed:	4/19/2022 10:40:14 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	10.336	4316485	97.28	225431
2	15.848	120527	2.72	4136